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DEVELOPING UNIVERSITY WORK-BASED LEARNING FOR ENGINEERING INDUSTRIES IN SUB-SAHARAN AFRICA: A CASE STUDY OF THE KINGDOM OF ESWATINI

J. S. Mahlalela¹

Department of Electrical & Electronics Engineering, University of Eswatini
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2543-0854>

P. S. Dlamini

Institute of Distance Education, University of Eswatini
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2201-6076>

C. J. M. Smith

Institute for University to Business Education, Glasgow Caledonian University
Glasgow, United Kingdom
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5708-6341>

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ABSTRACT

The 2021 UNESCO report 'Engineering for Sustainable Development' indicates the need for engineering education to shift its approach towards developing competencies capable of solving complex interdisciplinary problems. Moreover, the report highlights the role for a quality system to support lifelong learning of engineers and technologists. Additionally, the UK Royal Academy of Engineering (2020) recognised that there is a global shortage of engineering skills (in both quantity and potentially quality). Work-based learning, that sees co-creation and co-delivery of engineering programmes between university and industry, has the potential to address these challenges.

Whilst University accredited work-based learning (WBL) programmes are found in many countries, WBL is not currently a common approach in Sub-Saharan African engineering education. This paper will present results from an ongoing Royal Academy of Engineering funded project developing a work-based learning programme in engineering in the Kingdom of Eswatini– adopting a Log-Frame approach. The WBL programme is being co-designed by The University of Eswatini and local engineering industries with the aim of improving the quality and quantity of currently employed engineering practitioners. Specifically, the paper will highlight some of the emergent national and university policy dimensions supporting the development of WBL – such as a National Qualifications Framework and Recognition of Prior Learning – as well as questionnaire results indicating the

¹ Corresponding Author: J. S. Mahlalela. Email: jmahlalela@uniswa.sz

original awareness of WBL amongst industry and the subsequent need to raise awareness of WBL and its benefits. Finally, the adaptation of the curriculum development approaches that support co-creation of a WBL programme under Covid-19 restrictions will be shared.

1 INTRODUCTION

The UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) provide a global framework and call for action to improve the lives of all people over the coming decade. Engineers must be at the heart of achieving this and updated competences will be required for all Engineering Practitioners – from Technician to Engineer [1]. The development of such competences will require changes to engineering education to be able to tackle the acute problems of the next decade and beyond [2] and are likely to incorporate active and experiential learning and development of transversal skills to underpin lifelong learning and employability [3]. Whilst problem-based or practice-based learning (fusing academic and professional considerations) may be possible approaches [4], work-based learning (WBL) is an engaging and authentic approach that has been recognised as suitable in engineering education and for lifelong learning in the 21st Century [5].

Gibbs and Garnett [6] define work-based learning as a learning process that focuses university-level thinking upon work in an effort to facilitate the recognition, acquisition and application of knowledge learnt, skills and abilities acquired in the process [6]. Its purpose is to achieve specific learning outcomes that are of value to the learner, the workplace and the university, through a structured curriculum encompassing theory and practice; this partnership between students, employers and university is critical for design and sustainability of WBL programmes. Different types of work-based learning exist: at-work (company training); for-work (placement; internship) and through-work (linked to part-time study and accredited professional development in an organisational context) [7], indicating different WBL models. Such models allow for flexible access to Higher Education for a wider group of candidates. Unfortunately, the uptake of work-based learning shows geographic disparity that can be attributed to socio-economic and cultural factors, and has been more successfully adopted in countries like the UK, Australia and Germany. In Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) the adoption of WBL has been mainly in the Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) sector, with encouragement for a wider adoption of WBL to support skills development outcomes [8], including at university-level (where it is much less common).

Employers across the Sub-Saharan African region have already identified inadequately skilled workforces as a major constraint to their businesses [10]. Specifically, in the Kingdom of Eswatini, a skills gap analysis revealed that more than 80% of the sampled companies were not satisfied with the skill levels of the graduates produced by the TVET colleges in the Kingdom of Eswatini. The TVET throughputs are directly absorbed into industry, with the insufficient skill levels that calls for re-skilling/up-skilling of these candidates. Evidently, there is a need to adapt engineering education and find new pathways to develop more programmes and

align them to the needs of society and industry as well as encouraging entrepreneurship in the Kingdom of Eswatini. Additionally, the lack of engagement in advising and researching future skill needs, and the lack of dynamic industry informed curricula has been identified as a major barrier on the higher education system in the Kingdom of Eswatini [11]. This situation is compounded by the scarcity of Engineers in Sub-Saharan African countries per head of population and the vital role qualified engineers play in contributing to GDP [9].

The opportunity for WBL, as an engineering education approach, to build the required engineering competences in Sub-Saharan Africa, particularly in the Kingdom of Eswatini, has been introduced above. A Royal Academy of Engineering (RAE) funded project has a stated aim of developing one through-work, work-based learning programme in Engineering with the long-term goal of encouraging its adoption throughout Sub-Saharan Africa. This workstream partnered The University of Eswatini (UNESWA) with Glasgow Caledonian University (GCU). In the rest of this paper, the methodological approach will be outlined, followed by the developments and insights so far in this project, before summarising and outlining the next steps.

2 METHODOLOGY

The WBL workstream aim requires a transformative approach that engages relevant stakeholders (in university, in industry and in government) in a sustainable change to a new engineering education approach, one that will deliver engineers with the desired competences to address the long-term needs of society.

The complexity of the transformational process necessitated a structured approach to plan and evaluate the project and its success. A Logical Framework (Log-Frame) approach was adopted [12], as it provided a hierarchical and logic-driven approach to planning that engages stakeholders, and has been used in a wide-range of different interventions, and was supported by RAE (funders). As an intervention tool, Log-Frames help to identify activities (work-streams), and detail how the success of the project intervention will be evaluated and verified, as well as offering flexibility in how the activities need to be managed to achieve the outcomes.

The project-specific Log-Frame was developed through a series of workshops in January and February 2020 (pre-COVID) by university staff – at UNESWA and GCU (Table 1) that took a strategic view of the potential for WBL (so beyond the needs of the RAE project) to lay sustainable foundations for WBL in the Kingdom of Eswatini. It is noted as a limitation of this research that the envisaged engagements with other stakeholders were not possible at that time due to the onset of COVID-19 and lockdowns – implications of this are discussed below. This paper will evaluate the key activities undertaken to-date using the Log-Frame as a basis, as well as the value of Log-Frame for such developments. At this stage of the project, and as a result of delays from COVID-19, progress has been made in work streams (i) andragogical model and (ii) communication and engagement plan and form the focus of the detailed research presented in this paper. In particular, results will focus on a) policy ecosystem gap analysis and implications and potential opportunity identification; b) engagement with industry around opportunity for understanding of

WBL to-date; and c) development of UNESWA staff through knowledge exchange and training. Specific data collection and analysis methods are presented with the activities below in the results section.

Table 1. Abridged Log-Frame document for this project

	Area of intervention	Indicators of achievement	Means of verification	Risks & assumptions
Overall objectives	Contribute to the economic and social growth of the Kingdom of Eswatini through the development of a co-created work-based approach to engineering education	Industry improvements; Uptake to new learning pathways for engineering practitioners	Company results Country socio-economic indicators	Strategic buy in; Funding
Project purpose	To co-create with industry sustainable workforce with relevant and applied competences through WBL programme pilot	Successful pilot programme WBL Graduates	Surveys of stakeholders Number of WBL Graduates Case studies	Capacity and capability in stakeholders to develop WBL programme & support demand from industry
Expected results	1. Andragogical model for WBL	Gap analysis HE ecosystem; WBL Blueprint at UNESWA	Gap-analysis report Knowledge exchange visits;	Ecosystem supportive of project Staffing and CPD engagement around WBL Existing positive relationships with stakeholders (industry and ministries)
	2. Sustainable business model	Industries signed-up; Agreed business model	MOUs and contracts	
	3. Successful communications & engagement plan	Engagement events; Website	Attendance lists; Website engagement	
	4. Pilot programme developed and approved	Sufficiently trained staff in WBL; Programme approved	Training evaluation & materials; Programme approved	
Activities	Workstreams below managed via project plan: 1. WBL workstream project management; 2. Andragogic model; 3. Business model; 4. Comms & engagement; 5. UNESWA WBL project team development; 6. Pilot programme development			

3 RESULTS

3.1 National and University Policy gap analysis

The development of any new educational approach needs to be possible within the national and institutional policy landscape. As such, a key question posed was “Is the policy landscape supportive of pursuing a through-work, work-based learning approach in the Kingdom of Eswatini and at UNESWA?” This question was addressed through a comparative document-based gap-analysis, looking at the national Higher Education policy landscape, as well as at university-level policy. As identified in section 1 above, through-work WBL has potential for widening participation and offering flexible pathways. This is only possible if there is a National Credit and Qualifications Framework in place that supports progression through the levels by different learning pathways [13], as well as an outcome-based approach to learning. As such, policies included related to National Qualifications and Credit Framework, Recognition of Prior (informal) Learning, and Teaching and Learning Policies. As can be seen, whilst some gaps were initially identified, actions are now in place to address any gaps.

Table 2: Gap Analysis of UNESWA policies against enabling policies for WBL

Policy	Eswatini/UNESWA status	Comment
National Qualifications and Credit Framework	Framework launched officially April 2021; In transition as UNESWA needs to adopt the framework, including credit definition.	Timing supportive of WBL programme development.
Learning outcome based curriculum design approach	In transition: UNESWA Teaching, Learning and Assessment Policy Framework proposes all programmes to be learning outcome based by 2022	Policy direction supportive of WBL programme development
Recognition of Prior (informal) Learning	Policy not in place yet. Policy to go to Senate before end of 2021	Policy direction supportive of WBL programme development
Teaching, Learning and Assessment Policy Framework	Policy in place, including policy on Blended Learning (envisaged as possible strategy for delivery)	Policies in place. Recent pivot to on-line due to COVID-19 supportive of possible WBL delivery models.

Another national consideration is around the Professional and Regulatory Body for the profession, and their requirements and support for university-level WBL. Within the Southern African Development Countries of Sub-Saharan Africa region, engineering programmes may also refer and benchmark against the Engineering Council of South Africa (ECSA). Whilst ECSA requires WBL (placements) for Diploma qualifications, it is not as clear as to their position around university-level

WBL and a through-work WBL approach (that embraces authentic learning and assessment). At this stage, this is an area for further analysis and discussions.

This gap analysis activity highlighted also that currently it was difficult for vertical progression within the Qualifications Framework, for example someone with a Diploma qualification to proceed to study to degree level at University and get recognition for their prior learning. Consequently, such engineering practitioners have been identified as a potential group for whom a university-level WBL programme would be attractive and beneficial, and would be supported by ongoing evolution in National and university policies.

3.2 Industry and stakeholder understanding of WBL

A key assumption made in the Log-Frame above was that industry was receptive to and would engage with a through-work WBL programme. An online-survey was used to evaluate the perspective of a purposive sample of engineering industries in the Kingdom of Eswatini around their use and experiences of different forms of WBL to test that assumption. Purposive sampling was chosen to reflect the need to include industries of different sizes and within related technical fields that form important parts of the country's economy (with a mind to the goal of designing one WBL programme). A sample of seventeen (17) companies were invited to participate in a questionnaire with a mixture of closed, rating and open responses, of which nine (9) responded to the questionnaire. This showed a response rate of 53%; such a positive response-rate was likely obtained as the companies were asked to voluntarily participate through an invitation letter from UNESWA's Vice Chancellor. A suitably diverse range of companies participated (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Categories of participating companies

Fig. 2 Potential Candidates for the proposed WBL Model (distinguishing between those with degree and above (solid shading), with those with sub-degree qualifications (shaded))

Fig.2 indicates more employees with Diploma and Certificate qualifications (as compared to Bachelor or postgraduate qualifications), and confirms that the proposed target for the pilot WBL programme (offering pathway from existing qualification to degree) would have approximately 1000 candidates (based just on sampled companies). Additionally, there is the potential for developing a postgraduate qualification also, based on the data above.

Fig. 3 indicates the current awareness of the different forms of WBL in the Kingdom of Eswatini, and shows existing engagement with internships and apprenticeships, similarly to a previous study [11]. This previous study highlights low levels of cooperation between industry and academia, as well as companies holding the view that apprenticeships and internships are expensive, that industries are not-well developed to provide internships/apprenticeships, and lack the time and resources to train TVET trainees on practical industry skills. Consequently, this paper proposes a cooperative education (through-work WBL) programme that will help in upskilling engineering practitioners while they remain at work in employment. However, the results in Fig. 3 revealed that few companies (11% of respondents) were familiar with the cooperative education model proposed. This result shows the need for future workshops with stakeholders (industry, employers, regulatory bodies and government) to enable successful collaboration– an adaptation that was made to the project plan (reflecting that a Log-Frame is a live and adaptable document). The first of several ongoing engagement events with these key stakeholders has already taken place and more are planned.

Fig. 3 Company respondents Familiarity with various WBL Models

All respondents indicated a need to upskill and reskill their Engineering and Technical Practitioners with a particular desire for the focus to be in the discipline and technical areas of Electrical, Electronics and Software Engineering.

The survey (as an initial step in engaging a key stakeholder group) has indicated that there is need for closer and ongoing collaboration between industry and academia (and other stakeholders) to support development of Engineering Practitioners, with the above discipline areas having been identified as the initial potential focus areas for the development of the WBL pilot programme.

3.3 Staff development through knowledge exchange and training

University-level WBL was new to the Kingdom of Eswatini so a key consideration for this project was “how best to enable UNESWA to adopt a curriculum development approach suitable for a through-work WBL programme?” The original

project plan envisaged knowledge-exchange staff placements (from UNESWA to GCU and vice-versa), where workshop activities (aligned to stakeholder approach embodied in Log-Frame) would have helped achieve these outcomes. The outcome-focused approach of the Log-Frame encouraged the project team to adapt to COVID-19 circumstances (again reflecting the live nature of the Log-Frame document). A series of knowledge-exchange webinars (using Zoom) led by GCU took place. The webinar series aimed for participants to have a clear appreciation of what WBL in Engineering is, and to be able to plan the next steps in designing a WBL Engineering programme. An evaluation of the objectives through a paper-based questionnaire was undertaken after the series. The results indicated that the objectives were achieved; respondents appreciated the importance of the tripartite nature (university-employer-student partnership) in WBL in “both crafting and running the WBL programme”.

In terms of supporting the UNESWA WBL team to develop the work-based engineering programme, an on-line method of programme development that focused on a learning-outcome, graduate-focussed approach was required. At the current stage of the project, the plan is to use a Signature Pedagogy approach, enabled by an online whiteboard approach to develop this work-based learning programme. These design activities are planned to take place later in 2021, after further stakeholder engagement to build further consensus and support to university through-work WBL in the Kingdom of Eswatini, as identified in section 3.2 above.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

A Log-Frame approach is being used to support the co-design of a work-based learning (WBL) programme in Engineering. The approach outlined above has highlighted the importance of policies enabling a through-work WBL programme, the current lack of understanding of through-work WBL (co-operative education) amongst Engineering Industries in the Kingdom of Eswatini, and a current demand for WBL, particularly in Electronics, Electrical and Software Engineering fields. Further ongoing engagement with key stakeholders is embedded within the operational plans to achieve the deliverables and to truly develop a WBL Engineering programme appropriate to the Kingdom of Eswatini. The flexibility of the Log-Frame – as a living document - has allowed the project to continue to make consistent progress. Whilst there are ongoing limitations, due to COVID-19 pandemic, of not being able to involve wider stakeholders in development of Log-Frame and as comprehensive an evaluation of deliverables as desired, it is evident that the Log-Frame is still a valid approach (even if the more granular plans have had to adapt). Such a Log-Frame approach could be adopted by other institutions and countries interested in adopting through-work WBL or making significant changes to engineering education. The authors acknowledge the support of the UK Royal Academy of Engineering funding for this project under the Higher Education Partnerships in Sub-Saharan Africa fund.

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